

THE IMPORTANCE OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES OF DEPUTY DIRECTORS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to highlighting the role and importance of a competency-based approach in improving the management activities of deputy directors in preschool educational organizations. In the modern education system, the activities of senior managers depend not only on theoretical knowledge, but also on practical management skills and the ability to make quick and effective decisions in problematic situations.

The competence-based approach allows for a comprehensive assessment of the activities of senior managers, that is, it ensures a combination of knowledge, skills, experience, and personal qualities. The study analyzes the development of deputy principals' managerial activities, their professional potential, and the improvement of the quality of education based on this approach.

The article also highlights the effectiveness of modular trainings, practical seminars, and mentoring mechanisms, as well as ways to ensure the professional growth of managerial personnel through the organization of a monitoring system based on a competency model.

Materials and methods

The following methods were used in the research process:

- Scientific analysis and synthesis – in summarizing the theoretical foundations of the competence-based approach;

- Observation method – in studying managerial activities in preschool educational institutions;

- Questionnaire and interview – to determine the opinions of deputy directors and teaching staff;
- Diagnostic assessment – to determine the level of development of management competencies;
- Comparison method – when comparing the effectiveness of management based on the traditional and competence-based approaches.

The results of the study showed that modular trainings, practical seminars, and a mentoring system are effective tools for developing managerial competencies. In addition, a monitoring system based on a competency model allows for regular monitoring and evaluation of the professional development of managerial personnel.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that a competency-based approach is important in improving the managerial activities of deputy directors in preschool educational institutions. This approach serves to develop not only the knowledge level of senior managers, but also their practical management skills, ability to make decisions in problematic situations, and leadership qualities.

Professional competencies of deputy directors are systematically developed through module-based training programs, practical seminars and mentoring activities. This leads to an increase in their management efficiency and improvement of the educational process.

Also, establishing a monitoring system based on a competency model allows for assessing the professional growth of senior managers, eliminating identified shortcomings, and ensuring continuous development.

1.Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". – Tashkent, 2020.

2.Preschool Education and– Tashkent, 2018.allows you to assess the professional growth of employees, eliminate identified shortcomings, and ensure continuous development.

In general, the competence-based approach is an important factor in ensuring effective management in preschool educational organizations, increasing the professional potential of leadership personnel, and improving the quality of education.

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